

On the Presence of Maclurin in the Sapwood of the Cutch-producing Acacias.

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The yellow colour of the sapwood, if compared with the red-brown colour of the heart-wood, is very striking in the cutch-producing acacias, and since quercetin has been shown to be present in cutch (Löwe, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1874, **13**, 113; Hlasiwetz, *Annalen*, 1877, **186**, 327; Gauthier, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1873, **30**, 567; Perkin and Yoshitake, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, **81**, 1167), it seemed likely that the sapwood may contain quercetin. It has now been shown that this is not the case, as the sapwood of *Acacia catechu*, *A. Catechuoides* and *A. Sundra* has been found to contain maclurin only. The absence of quercetin in the cutch-producing plants thus confirms the contention (Nierenstein, *Ber.*, 1923, **56**, 1877) that quercetin, if present in cutch, is of foreign origin. All attempts to co-ordinate the chemistry of catechin with that of quercetin (Hlasiwetz, *loc. cit.*; Perkin and Yoshitake, *loc. cit.*; Ryan and Walsh, *Proc. Roy. Soc. Dublin*, 1906, **15**, 113) are thus obviously unjustifiable. On the other hand, the presence of maclurin (IV) in the sapwood provides interesting evidence as to the place of catechin in the metabolism of these acacias. It has already been pointed out (Nierenstein, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 1672) that since catechin is only found in the heart-wood, it must be a final product of metabolism. This was confirmed by the discovery of *l*-leucomaclurin-glycol ether (II) in the young twigs of *Acacia Catechu*. It will be realised that the production of acacatechin (I) and isoacacatechin (III) from *l*-leucomaclurin-glycol ether (II) follows as a matter of fact, and this was confirmed experimentally in the case of acacatechin, when it was shown that *l*-leucomaclurin-glycol ether on boiling with acetic anhydride yields penta-acetyl-*l*-acacatechin (Nierenstein, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 1676). This obviously goes to show that *l*-leucomaclurin-glycol ether (II), which is present in the young twigs,

is the first product of metabolism, from which (i) maclurin (IV) is produced in the sapwood on hydrolysis and oxidation, in the same manner as it is formed when acacatechin (I) is reacted on by *Penicillium solitam* (Hazleton and Nierenstein, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **46**, 2100) and (ii) the two water-insoluble catechins, (I) and (III), are deposited in the heart-wood by the intramolecular loss of water.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The sapwood of the three acacias investigated separately was obtained by turning the logs freed from the bark in a lathe. It was exhaustively extracted with ethyl acetate in a large Soxhlet apparatus. The residue left on evaporation of the ethyl acetate was dissolved in water, and the aqueous solution shaken with fat-free caseinogen to remove tannins (*cf.* Körner and Nierenstein, *Chem. Z.*, 1911, **36**, 31; Nierenstein, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **115**, 1330). The filtered solution gave on concentration *in vacuo* crude maclurin (average yield 0.4 g. from 1 kg. sapwood), which on several recrystallisations from

water melted in the anhydrous state (dried at 100° in a vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide) at 220-22°, but became resinous at about 208-10°. On methylation with diazomethane in the manner already described (Hazleton and Nierenstein, *loc. cit.*, p. 2104) the well-crystallising pentamethyl-derivative melting correctly at 157° was obtained. (Found: C, 65·23; H, 6·21. $C_{18}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 65·17; H, 5·98 per cent.). The pentamethyl ether was found to be in every respect identical with authentic pentamethylmaclurin (mixed m. p. 157°).

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